

Degrowth vs. Green Growth: Multidimensional Impacts on Economy, Society, and Planetary Boundaries

Abstract

We employ a quantitative system dynamics model to examine the evolution of key economic, social, and biophysical variables under two contrasting development pathways: green growth (GG) and degrowth (DG). To enable a multidimensional assessment of environmental outcomes, we develop a set of planetary boundary indices that capture the degree of transgression of critical Earth system thresholds. Scenario simulations reveal broadly similar trajectories for GG and DG until the middle of the century, after which key variables diverge markedly. Results indicate that absolute decoupling of fossil energy consumption from economic growth in the GG scenario is insufficient to halt or reverse the deterioration of most planetary boundary variables. Instead, rising consumption levels across all social classes and world regions drive the Earth system irreversibly into a high-risk zone. In contrast, the DG scenario yields lower overall economic output but substantially improves the living standards of poorer populations and those in less developed regions, while the transgression of planetary boundaries is slowed or even reversed. Overall, the DG scenario outperforms GG in 10 out of 11 planetary boundary indices. Nevertheless, even under ambitious technological and social DG policies, the Earth system does not return to a safe operating space within the simulation period.

Keywords

Degrowth; Post-growth; Green growth; Earth system boundaries; convergence; integrated assessment models

1. Introduction

Despite a modest decoupling between global GDP and the adverse impacts of economic growth on planetary boundaries between 1995 and 2019 (Vázquez et al., 2023), recent assessments indicate that six of the nine planetary boundaries have already been transgressed (Richardson et al., 2023). The ‘safe and just’ operating space—defined by Earth System Boundaries that minimize exposure to significant harm to humans—is considerably narrower, implying an even higher degree of transgression and associated risks (Rockström et al., 2023). Accordingly, sustainability science is tasked with identifying development pathways capable of meeting basic human needs for the entire world population without driving the Earth system beyond the planetary conditions delineating the safe operating space (O’Neill et al., 2018). Although climate change occupies a central position in the planetary boundaries framework, the latter cannot be reduced to the former but rather opens up the possibility to study interactions between different planetary boundaries, such as feedback dynamics between land system change and climate change (Drüke et al., 2024). Moreover, global environmental change is increasingly understood as a co-evolutionary process between human societies and the biogeophysical Earth system, rather than a unidirectional causal relationship driven solely by anthropogenic pressures. This perspective can be represented through ‘World–Earth’ models that integrate socio-economic dynamics alongside a biophysical systems (Donges et al., 2019).

Within debates on sustainable future development pathways, proponents of ‘degrowth’ and ‘post-growth’ contend that reducing consumption in the Global North, coupled with reconfiguring development trajectories in the Global South away from accumulation by dispossession, is essential to achieving human well-being within a safe operating space for humanity (Kallis et al., 2025; Kronenberg et al., 2024; Sultana, 2023). However, model-based evidence demonstrating the potential of global degrowth or post-growth scenarios to reduce planetary boundary transgressions remains limited. Several factors contribute to this gap. First, quantitative modeling studies that simulate future impacts of global development pathways on Earth system boundaries often incorporate only a subset of planetary boundaries (e.g. Allen et al., 2021; Mathias et al., 2017) or operationalize them in abstract, non-biophysical terms (Gries & Naudé, 2025). Second, those studies integrating a high number of planetary boundaries either do not focus on the question of economic growth (Algunaibet et al., 2019; Engström et al., 2020) or explore different forms of green growth scenarios characterized by continuous GDP expansion (Van Vuuren et al., 2025). Finally, modeling studies associated with the degrowth or post-growth discourse tend to be conceptual or limited to the climate–economy nexus, thereby neglecting other planetary boundaries (Lauer et al., 2025). The absence of degrowth scenarios in classical Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) can be attributed to a pro-growth bias within the IAM community, embedded in both modeling tools and modeling practice (Cointe & Pottier, 2023). Although there is no *ex ante* impossibility of simulating degrowth trajectories within IAMs (Kikstra et al., 2024), prevailing modeling conventions often constrain their capacity to represent post-growth futures (Edwards et al., 2025).

In this study, we address these gaps through a multidimensional quantitative assessment of global ‘green growth’ and ‘degrowth’ futures, evaluating their social, economic, and environmental implications. To this end, we integrate planetary boundaries into a system-dynamics-based IAM of medium complexity capable of representing non-linear economic trajectories and convergence dynamics among different social classes and world regions. By simulating both scenarios within a single modeling framework, this study constitutes the first

systematic comparison of the potential implications of degrowth and green-growth pathways for the transgression of multiple planetary boundaries.

2. Methods

2.1. Model overview

We use MORDRED 1.1 (Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development) to parametrize and run the scenarios. MORDRED is a data-based system dynamic model documented in Lauer & Llases (2025). For brevity, this section summarizes only the model's key characteristics and principal variables.

MORDRED comprises seven interrelated modules: population, economy, labor, energy, land, climate, and environmental stressors. The main data sources forming its quantitative basis are the environmentally and socially extended input–output (IO) tables from Exiobase3 (Stadler et al., 2018), consumption inequality estimates from the GCIP database (Lahoti et al., 2016), UN population data (UN DESA, 2019), climate and emissions data from the IPCC WGI (2021) and fossil resource estimates from BGR (2020). The model's main purpose is to enable data-informed scenario analyses that explore conceptual and theoretical questions rather than to provide probabilistic forecasts of key variables.

The economic module follows an input-output (IO) structure and includes all typical variables of IO models: of IO models: an A matrix, output at the sector level, final demand components (private consumption, public consumption, and gross fixed capital formation), and sectoral capital stocks. The model distinguishes 25 sectors, enabling users to analyze multiple energy-related industries (see Section 1 of the Supplementary Material). Total output is driven by exogenously defined growth rates for the poorest household type, as well as by consumption shares of households, governments, and investors that reflect either empirical data or scenario assumptions.

Economic production depends on labor, land, and energy inputs, which are derived from their respective modules. Production requires four land types—food (cropland and grassland), forest, land for energy generation and infrastructure, and 'other land' as defined by FAO. The remaining land types in the model include (non-economically used) primary forest, secondary forest and shrub. Non-economic land categories include primary forest, secondary forest, and shrubland. Economic activity is also linked to environmental stressors, including greenhouse gas emissions, which are computed in the environmental stressors module and fed into the climate module. Production may be limited by input scarcity or by adverse climate impacts on economic structure; however, this latter feedback is deactivated in the simulations to reduce model complexity.

The global population, which supplies labor and consumes most economic output, is divided into three world regions and three household types ("classes") per region. The *center* includes high-income countries, the *semiperiphery* upper-middle-income countries, and the *periphery* lower-middle- and low-income countries. In each region, the richest 20% constitute the T20 (Top20) class, the middle 50% the M50 class, and the poorest 30% the B30 (Bottom30) class. Fertility and mortality rates depend on class-specific consumption trajectories and evolve dynamically throughout the simulation period.

2.2. Planetary Boundary Indices

To conduct the scenario analysis, we extended MORDRED 1.1 with a Planetary Boundary Indices (PBI) module. This module calculates several PBIs based on Steffen et al. (2015), Richardson et al. (2023) and model output variables. Each PBI operationalizes a planetary boundary within the limits of what the model can represent. All indices are normalized to a reference value of 100 at the simulation's starting year. Deterioration in a boundary variable is reflected as an increase in its index.

Except for aerosol loading and green freshwater, all PBIs include lower and upper threshold values. The lower threshold corresponds to the planetary boundary, while the upper threshold represents the upper end of the 'zone of increasing risk' defined by Richardson et al. (2023). For 'novel entities', we set the lower threshold to 1 and the upper to 95, given that this boundary is already considered transgressed. The boundaries for green freshwater change and atmospheric aerosol loading cannot be represented in MORDRED, as their biophysical variables are sub-global, whereas MORDRED operates at a global scale. For blue freshwater, the thresholds are derived from the uncertainty range for global blue water use reported in Steffen et al. (2015).

Values above the lower threshold indicate entry into a zone of increasing risk or zone of uncertainty while values above the upper threshold correspond to a zone of high risk, where interglacial Earth system conditions are confidently exceeded. The greater the transgression, the higher the probability of abrupt and potentially catastrophic changes in the Earth system or regional subsystems (Richardson et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2009). Values below the lower threshold indicate a safe operating zone. Notably, the simulations begin with several PBIs already in the high-risk zone.

The first two PBIs are related to the climate change boundary and are calculated with two model variables: atmospheric CO₂ concentration (ppm) and effective radiative forcing (W/m²):

$$CO_2 \text{ concentration index} = \frac{\text{atmospheric } CO_2 \text{ concentration}_t}{\text{atmospheric } CO_2 \text{ concentration}_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Radiative forcing index} = \frac{ERF_t}{ERF_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

The PBI for ocean acidification is calculated with the aragonite saturation variable in the model.

$$\text{Ocean acidification index} = 200 - \left(\frac{\text{aragonite saturation}_t}{\text{aragonite saturation}_{t_0}} * 100 \right) \quad (3)$$

The PBI for biosphere integrity is calculated based on the different land use types in MORDRED and assumptions about the intensity with which the different land uses appropriate the Net Primary Production (NPP) of the biosphere. Infrastructure is assumed to have the highest appropriation (destruction) of NPP whereas HANPP (Human Appropriation of NPP) is assumed to be zero in the case of land types that are not subject to economic use. The estimated HANPP for the initial year of the simulation is 0.3, in line with Richardson et al. (2023).

$$HANPP_{Mordred} = \frac{\sum_{land \ type=1}^9 \alpha_{land \ type} * size_{land \ type}}{\sum_{land \ type=1}^9 size_{land \ type}} \quad (4)$$

$land \ type \in \{infrastructure, energy, food \ (high \ intensity), food \ (low \ intensity), productive \ forest, other \ land, primary \ forest, secondary \ forest, shrub\}$

$$1 > \alpha_1 > \alpha_2 > \alpha_3 > \alpha_4 > \alpha_5 > \alpha_6 > \alpha_{7,8,9} \geq 0$$

$$Biosphere\ integrity\ index = \frac{HANPP_{Mordred_t}}{HANPP_{Mordred_{t_0}}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

The PBI for land-system change is calculated with changes in forest land types in the model. The forest cover in the initial year of the simulation is derived by aggregating primary forest, secondary forest and productive, i.e. economically used forest, and is assumed to constitute 60% of the original forest cover, following Richardson et al. (2023).

$$\begin{aligned} Land\ system\ change\ index & \quad (6) \\ & = 200 - \frac{(land\ type_4 + land\ type_6 + land\ type_7)_t}{(land\ type_4 + land\ type_6 + land\ type_7)_{t_0}} * 100 \end{aligned}$$

The PBIs for biogeochemical flows are approximated with two model variables. Industrial N fixation is approximated as a share of the model variable *material extraction of chemical and fertilizer minerals* and in the initial moment of the simulation reflects the current value given in Richardson et al. (2023). P flows from fertilizers to erodible soils are approximated by the model variable *phosphorus soil pollution of agriculture*. The initial value for the variable is based on estimates of P flows to soils by Lu & Tian (2017).

$$Industrial\ N\ fixation_{2019} = \alpha * Chemical\ and\ fertilizer\ minerals_{2019} \quad (7)$$

$$P\ soil\ pollution_{t_0} = P_{2013} + 6 * \frac{P_{2013} - P_{1961}}{1961 - 2013} \quad (8)$$

$$Biogeochemical\ flows\ index_N = \frac{Chemical\ and\ fertilizer\ minerals_t}{Chemical\ and\ fertilizer\ minerals_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (9)$$

$$Biogeochemical\ flows\ index_P = \frac{P\ soil\ pollution_t}{P\ soil\ pollution_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (10)$$

The lower (l) and upper (u) threshold values for the seven indices were calculated on the basis of the lower and upper thresholds given by Richardson et al. (2023).

$$\begin{aligned} i \in \{l, u\} & \quad (11) \\ Threshold_{i_{CO2\ concentration}} & = \frac{threshold\ value_i}{atmospheric\ CO2\ concentration_{t_0}} * 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$Threshold_{i_{forcing}} = \frac{threshold\ value_i}{ERF_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (12)$$

$$Thresholds_{i_{ocean\ acidification}} = 200 - \left(\frac{threshold\ value_i}{aragonite\ saturation_{t_0}} \right) * 100 \quad (13)$$

$$Thresholds_{i_{functional\ integrity}} = \left(\frac{threshold\ value_i}{HANPP_{MORDRED_{t_0}} * 100} \right) * 100 \quad (14)$$

$$Thresholds_{i_{land\ system\ change}} = 200 - \left(\frac{threshold\ value_i}{60} \right) * 100 \quad (15)$$

$$Thresholds_{i_N} = \frac{threshold\ value_i}{Industrial\ N\ fixation_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (16)$$

$$Thresholds_{i_P} = \frac{threshold\ value_i}{P\ flows\ to\ soils_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (17)$$

MORDRED does not contain information on the percentage of synthetic chemicals that are released into the environment without safety testing. However, we assume that the quantity of novel entities is proportional to the production of the chemical sector. Thus, the PBI for novel entities is calculated with the output of the chemical industry. Similarly, the aerosol loading index is approximated using PM2.5, PM10, and NH3 pollution, as the model lacks data on interhemispheric aerosol optical depth differences.

$$Novel\ entities\ index = \frac{x_{9t}}{x_{9t_0}} * 100 \quad (18)$$

$$Aerosol\ loading\ index = \frac{PM_{2.5t} + PM_{10t} + NH3_t}{PM_{2.5t_0} + PM_{10t_0} + NH3_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (19)$$

Because MORDRED does not explicitly model human-induced disturbances of blue or green water flows, freshwater use PBIs are approximated through household and industrial blue water consumption and green water use in the food sector. For blue water, threshold values are based on the uncertainty range in Steffen et al. (2015). The Exiobase3 data yield an initial blue water estimate roughly 30% lower than Steffen et al.'s value, which may slightly overestimate the corresponding thresholds.

$$Blue\ water\ index = \frac{(consumption_{blue_{hh}} + consumption_{blue_{industries}})_t}{(consumption_{blue_{hh}} + consumption_{blue_{industries}})_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (20)$$

$$Green\ water\ index = \frac{water\ consumption_{green_t}}{water\ consumption_{green_{t_0}}} * 100 \quad (21)$$

$$Thresholds_{i_{blue\ water}} = \frac{threshold\ value_i}{total\ blue\ water\ consumption_{t_0}} * 100 \quad (22)$$

The stratospheric ozone depletion index remains constant, as ozone changes are not modeled in MORDRED. Threshold values follow Richardson et al. (2023).

$$Ozone\ depletion\ index = 100 \quad (23)$$

$$Thresholds_{ozone_i} = 200 - \left(\frac{threshold_i}{284.6\ DU} \right) * 100 \quad (24)$$

Table 1 summarizes the operationalization of the planetary boundaries in MORDRED and the corresponding lower and upper threshold values.

Planetary boundary	approximation	lower threshold	upper threshold

Climate change	atmospheric CO2 concentration	85	110
	effective radiative forcing	37	56
Ocean acidification	aragonite saturation	93	100
Biosphere integrity	land use intensity and shares of different land types	33	66
Land-system change	% forest cover in original forest cover	75	110
Biogeochemical flows	fertilizer extraction	33	43
	P flows to soils	33	59
Novel entities	output chemical industry	1	95
Aerosol loading	industrial NH3, PM2.5 and PM10 emissions	na	na
Blue freshwater change	household and industry blue water consumption	223	335
Green freshwater change	green water consumption	na	na
Stratospheric ozone depletion	constant value	103	108

Table 1: Overview of planetary boundary representation in MORDRED.

2.3. Scenario design

We construct two stylized scenarios reflecting distinct economic paradigms: Green Growth (GG) and Degrowth (DG). Both represent idealized transitions characterized by ambitious environmental policy assumptions. Simulations run from 2019 to 2100. Unlike other green-growth or post-growth scenario exercises (Nieto et al., 2020; Van Vuuren et al., 2017), we do not impose scenario-specific exogenous demographic assumptions, as mortality and fertility rates are endogenized in MORDRED. Moreover, unlike the International Futures model used by Moyer (2023) to simulate degrowth trajectories, demographic parameters in MORDRED depend primarily on consumption per capita rather than education or GDP per capita.

The GG scenario represents a continuation of historical development trends combined with strong green-technology deployment for global decarbonization. Economic output, labor productivity, and land productivity increase continuously throughout the century. Consumption inequality declines moderately, while all social classes and world regions experience rising consumption levels. The electricity mix becomes increasingly green, with rapid electrification and a major expansion of renewable generation. Fossil energy is progressively replaced by modern bioenergy. Agricultural intensification increases blue water use and decreases green water use.

The DG scenario entails a radical shift in global development patterns. Per capita household consumption levels converge by 2035 toward a common level of approximately €9,000 per person per year. By 2100, electricity generation relies entirely on renewable sources, and economic electrification expands—though less than in the GG scenario. As in the GG scenario, half of fossil inputs are replaced by biomass energy. Agriculture transitions from conventional to organic production, and a fully plant-based global diet is adopted. Despite this shift, land productivity continues to increase, partly due to a higher share of irrigated agriculture and reduced rain-fed production. Labor productivity also rises, though at a slower rate than under the GG scenario.

Table 2 summarizes key changes in the GG and the DG scenario while additional details on the parametrization process is provided in Section 2 of the Supplementary Material.

	GG	DG
Δ per capita consumption center	++	--
Δ per capita consumption semiperiphery	+++	+
Δ per capita consumption periphery	+++	++
Δ electrification	++	+
Δ share of renewables in electricity mix	+++	+++
Δ ratio bioenergy to fossil energy	+++	+++
Δ blue water intensity (industries)	+	+
Δ blue water intensity (households)	0	-
Δ green water intensity (industries)	-	-
Δ N ₂ O and CH ₄ emission intensities	0	-- (organic agriculture + plant-based diet)
Δ N&P pollution intensity of agriculture	0	-- (organic agriculture)
Δ Labor productivity	++	+
Δ Land intensity	---	--- - (plant-based diet) + (organic agriculture)

Table 2: Key changes in the GG and DG scenario.

3. Results

In the following, we present the main results of the scenario simulations, covering the evolution of macroeconomic, social and biophysical variables.

3.1. Macroeconomic developments

Global world output follows a comparable trajectory in both scenarios until the mid-2050s, although output grows slightly slower in the DG scenario. From 2060 onwards, growth in output accelerates in the GG scenario and at the end of the century is 3.9 times its initial value. Conversely, in the DG scenario output peaks at a level 1.6 times the initial value in 2055 and afterwards declines continuously. Towards the end of the century, world output reaches a level comparable to 2040s, which is 27% above current output values. By 2100, output in the GG scenario is three times higher than in DG. Notably, downscaling consumption and production in richer regions does not reduce total output during the first 30 years; significant divergence between DG and GG only appears due to the continued application of DG policies throughout the century.

Total capital stock begins to differ between scenarios from the mid-2020s, accumulating faster in GG than in DG. By 2060, capital stock in GG is 1.35 times higher than in DG. In the DG scenario, total capital peaks later than output and remains nearly constant between 2060 and 2100. Compared to 2019, world capital stock doubles under DG and grows 6.5-fold under GG.

Total government spending (world public consumption) follows the same patterns as total output in both scenarios, with a continuous increase until the end of the century in the case of GG and a mid-century peak and subsequent slow decline in the case of DG. Until 2050, the difference in public consumption trajectories between DG and GG is even less pronounced than for the world output trajectories. In the DG scenario, between 2050 and 2070, world public consumption plateaus at 59% above its initial value while world output during the same time period first increases and then declines. By 2100, global public consumption in GG is 2.5 times higher than in DG.

Although global public consumption grows in both scenarios, regional trajectories diverge. In GG, consumption in the center grows slowly, plateauing between 2070 and 2090 before slightly declining. In the semiperiphery, it rises steadily, almost quadrupling by 2100. In the periphery, growth accelerates from 2040, increasing sevenfold by the end of the 21st century.

In DG, strong convergence until 2035 leads to an initial sharp drop in government consumption in the center—falling by 75% from initial levels within 15 years—followed by a brief recovery and then gradual decline. In the semiperiphery, consumption rises faster than in GG during the first three decades, equalizes around 2060, and then declines whereas it continues to grow in the GG scenario. The difference between DG and GG is even more pronounced for the public consumption of the periphery: by 2040, public consumption reaches €6.5 trillion in DG—2.5 times the GG level—and remains higher for five decades. This trend is only reversed from 2074 onwards, as a result of continued growth in the GG scenario and slow decline in the DG scenario. Nevertheless, at the end of the century, in the DG scenario, public consumption in the periphery is four times as high as in the center and slightly higher than in the semiperiphery.

Figure 1: Development of a) total output; b) total capital stock; c) total public consumption; d) public consumption in high-income countries; e) public consumption in upper-middle income countries; f) public consumption in lower-middle and low-income countries in a Degrowth (blue) and a Green growth (orange) scenario.

3.2. Social developments

Demographic developments in the two scenarios start to diverge from 2030 onwards, with higher population growth in the GG than in the DG scenario, driven by underlying changes in household consumption. However, in both scenarios, world population peaks at a relatively low level and declines moderately until the end of the century. In the GG scenario, population peaks at 8.83 billion in 2060, returning to 2020 levels by 2100. In the DG scenario, population peaks

earlier, at 8.56 billion in 2050, reaching the initial size in the 2070s and ending at 7 billion, 10% below the initial value..

As a result of a continuous increase in labor productivity assumed in both scenarios labor demand across all sectors declines much faster than world population. Due to greater labor productivity increases assumed for the GG scenarios, the decline in labor input is stronger in the first half of the simulation. This dynamic is reversed in the second half of the simulation due to the combined effects of increasing labor productivity and decreasing or stabilizing consumption levels. In the final year of the simulation, labor demand is reduced by 70.7 % in the DG scenario, and by 42.5 % in the GG scenario compared to the initial value. However, while in a DG scenario this result can be assessed as positive as it allows for the sharing of work and an increase in leisure time (Bilancini & D'Alessandro, 2012; Houtbeckers, 2025; Vincent & Brandellero, 2023), in a GG scenario the decline in labor demand constitutes a threat to job security (D'Alessandro et al., 2020). Increasing employment in the GG scenario would mean a further increase in growth rates, followed, *ceteris paribus*, by even higher environmental impacts. For the service sector, which is the greatest sector in MORDRED, in the GG scenario the demand for workers declines fast during the first decade of the simulation, stays constant during the following three decades and then starts to decline again at an accelerated rate. Conversely, in the DG scenario, after an initial fast decline, demand increases between 2030 and 2050, reaching almost 1.3 billion people in 2050 required to work in the service sector. However, after this peak demand starts to fall persistently until the end of the century. In 2100, in the GG scenario, 1.08 billion workers are projected to work in the service industry, compared to 1.25 billion in 2019, whereas in the DG scenario this number has dropped to 557 million workers. This finding suggests that in the DG scenario high labor productivity growth might be only required during the first three decades after which the scenario would also be feasible with constant or declining labor productivities that are below the current labor productivity rates in high-income countries.

The average consumption per capita in the global world economy follows a comparable trajectory in both scenarios until 2055. Thereafter, GG consumption continues to rise, while DG stabilizes at €9,165 per person. However, significant differences appear at the class level from the start. In the GG scenario, the richest 20% in the center steadily increase consumption while in the DG scenario the consumption of the T20 class falls sharply due to global convergence, dropping from €41,722 to €6,711 by 2035, below the target level of €9,000 which is only reached in 2052. This dynamic is also present in the consumption trajectories of the other classes of the center although it is less extreme. The middle class of the center that constitutes 50% of the population sees its consumption reduced by more than 50% during the first 15 years of the simulation while the consumption of the poorest 30% declines less sharply. Whereas the richest 20% of the center consume 8 times as much in a GG scenario compared to a DG scenario at the end of the century, the middle class of the center consumes 4 times as much, and the poorest 30% of the center two times as much.

In the semiperiphery, the per capita consumption of the T20 class increases faster in the GG scenario than in the DG scenario, reaching a consumption level more than 4 times as high as in the DG scenario at the end of the simulation. However, for the remaining 70% of the population in the semiperiphery, consumption levels increase faster in the DG scenario. In the case of the middle class, consumption levels in the GG scenario only exceed those in the DG scenario from 2065 onwards while for the poorest class consumption between the two scenarios only converges towards the end of the simulation.

Last, in the periphery the consumption of the middle class in the DG scenario increases exponentially during the first 15 years of the simulation after which consumption growth slows down slightly and levels off in the middle of the century. In the GG scenario, this class reaches comparable consumption levels only in 2080. Nevertheless, due to the accelerating growth in consumption in the GG scenario, in 2100 consumption levels are 58% higher. For the poorest class of the periphery, the DG scenario leads to a higher consumption trajectory throughout the whole simulation as annual per capita consumption under a GG development pathway only reaches 7,230 € in 2100 while in the DG scenario this value is already reached in 2039. Conversely, for the 20% richest in the periphery, consumption levels between DG and GG already converge in 2040, and in the final year of the simulation, consumption per capita in the GG scenario is more than three times as high as in the DG scenario.

Overall, DG benefits poorer classes in the periphery and semiperiphery in terms of both equity and absolute consumption, while GG favors high-income households, particularly the top 20%.

The consumption of all classes in the DG scenario in the first three decades of the simulation is limited by the rates at which land intensities in the model fall. As the DG scenario implies a fast and strong growth in the consumption of poorer classes that spend a larger share of their budgets on the food sector than richer classes, the land demand resulting from the desired growth in consumption is higher than the land available for use until 2055. However, continuous land intensity improvements combined with a continuous increase in wealth of the poorer classes, and a reversal of population growth eventually dissolves the land scarcity problem and the target consumption level is reached by all classes. Thus, the simulation illustrates a potential feasibility barrier of scenarios with fast rates and high degrees of convergence in consumption due to the requirement of high land productivity increases necessary to cover the increased consumption of food products resulting from a combination of population growth and increased affluence of the world's poorer classes.

As birth rates in MORDRED are determined by region- and class-specific consumption trajectories, the earlier peak in world population in the DG scenario can be explained by the faster growth in the consumption of the world's poorest classes that reduces birth rates.

Figure 2: Evolution of a) world population; b) workers demanded in the service sector; c) average consumption per capita; d) consumption per capita of the middle class in high-income countries; e) consumption per capita of the middle class in upper-middle income countries; f) consumption per capita of the middle class in lower-middle and low-income countries in a Degrowth (blue) and a Green growth (orange) scenario.

3.3. Biophysical developments

In the GG scenario, absolute decoupling between economic growth and fossil resource use occurs between 2020 and 2040 and between 2070 and 2100 with a phase of low growth in fossil resource use in between (Figure 3a). Despite absolute decoupling, the climate-related PBIs (Figure 3e-g) continue to deteriorate and remain in or cross the high-risk zone during the last four decades of the simulation. Ultimately, the pace of decoupling is not fast enough for effective climate mitigation: in the final year of the simulation, the level of global fossil resource use has only declined by 12% compared to the 2019 level. Conversely, in the DG scenario, total fossil resource consumption declines by 68.5%. Interestingly, the DG scenario also experiences a period of absolute decoupling in the first decade of the simulation, followed by relative decoupling until the 2050s. As fossil fuel intensity continues to decline throughout the century, the consequence of the eventual degrowth in world output in the DG scenario is a significant reduction of fossil resource extraction and consumption. Although the carbon intensity of the economy by 2100 is 9% lower under GG than under DG, total fossil resource consumption is 2.8 times higher due to the continued growth in output in the GG scenario during the second half of the century.

The absolute decoupling between economic growth and total fossil resource use that can be observed in the GG scenario stems from strong reductions in the consumption of those fossil resources that are used as energy sources. As shown in Figure 3b, the amount of fossil resources used for non-energy purposes, i.e. as industry feedstocks, continues to increase. In the DG scenario, the evolution of the material use of fossil resources is comparable to the GG scenario during the first three decades of the simulation but then diverges in line with differences in

world output between the two scenarios. As oil currently constitutes 73% of the fossil fuels that are used for non-energy purposes, in both scenarios the reduction of fossil fuel combustion 'saves' oil resources that are required as feedstock in industrial processes.

Comparing the simulation results of both scenarios across all PBIs, we find that the DG scenario outperforms the GG scenario in 10 of 11 indices (Figure 3c-l). This result is robust to changes of the scenario assumptions in favor of GG and against DG (see the sensitivity tests in S3 Supplementary Material). The exception is the PBI for land-system change, where DG performs better 2040–2080 and GG in the last two decades (Figure 3g). Under GG, no index value is compatible with a safe operating space while under DG only indices representing biogeochemical flows reach values corresponding to a safe operating space.

The radiative forcing index and the CO₂ concentration index, which belong to the climate change planetary boundary, worsen in both scenarios during the simulation (Figure 3c and d). In the GG scenario, the radiative forcing index increases from 100 in 2019 to 225 in 2100. In the DG scenario, the index peaks in 2081 at a value of 151 and in the last two decades of the simulation declines to 148. In the case of the CO₂ concentration index, both scenarios enter the high-risk zone between 2050 and 2060. In the GG simulation, the index worsens faster than in the DG simulation, reaching a final value 13% higher than in the DG scenario, and 31% higher than the initial value. The ocean acidification index mirrors the development of the two other climate-related indices (Figure 3e), with a stabilizing dynamic in the DG simulation, and continued deterioration for the GG simulation. The index value stays in the high-risk zone between 2027 and 2100 (GG), and between 2029 and 2100 (DG).

The biosphere integrity index starts already in a high-risk zone in 2019 and stays constant during the first 15 years for both scenarios. From 2035 onwards, the index worsens in the DG scenario but starts to improve by 2050. During the following 50 years of the simulation the value improves steadily and in 2080 crosses the upper threshold, reaching a zone of uncertainty. Although the index values continue to decline, the safe operating space is not reached during the simulation period. Conversely, in the GG simulation, the index value starts to increase from 2050 onwards, indicating that the Earth system progressively advances farther into the high-risk zone for this planetary boundary (Figure 3f). The differences in the performance between the two scenarios can be explained by the differences in land use in the scenarios: Under GG, the share of economically used land is higher than under DG. Thus, in the latter, natural ecosystems associated with higher biosphere integrity have space to recover while in the former the great majority of accessible land is 'managed' and economically exploited.

The land system change index starts in the zone of increasing risk, located between the safe operating zone and the high-risk zone, and stays there for both scenarios during the simulation period although it evolves towards the safe-operating zone during the simulation period (Figure 3g). The index starts to improve more than 10 years earlier in the DG scenario but then stays constant during the last 50 years of the simulation at a value of 88. In the GG scenario, the index starts to continuously improve from the year 2054 and in 2100 stands at 86. The index value is driven by changes in the forest cover throughout the simulations which increases earlier in the DG than in the GG scenario. Equally, between 2050 and 2100, the share of forest not subject to economic exploitation steadily increases in the DG scenario, compared to a steady increase in economically used forest in the GG scenario.

The differences between DG and GG are highest in the case of the planetary boundaries linked to biogeochemical flows (Figure 3h and i). Both indices start at the same point located above the

upper risk threshold but take very different trajectories. In the GG simulation the index values of both N and P flows increase continuously, reaching 474 and 275 in 2100 compared to the reference values of 100 in 2019. In the case of DG, the nitrogen flow index declines from 100 in 2019 to 73.9 in 2051, increases slightly to 78 in 2055 and afterwards declines continuously until the final year of the simulation. The N-flow index enters the zone of increasing risk in 2065, and the safe operating zone in 2087 where it remains until the end of the simulation. The P-flow index reaches the zone of uncertainty in 2084 and the safe operating zone in 2094. Interestingly, in our simulations, absolute decoupling between economic growth and the N- and P-boundary cannot be observed for GG but for DG during the time period in which world output grows. On the one hand, this shows that a period of green (macroeconomic) growth in a scenario of (consumption) degrowth is not a contradiction but a plausible result due to global consumption convergence combined with technological changes (conventional to organic agriculture) and behavioral changes (from meat-based to plant-based diet). On the other hand, it demonstrates that absolute decoupling in a GG scenario limited to fossil resource use is insufficient for the Earth system to leave the high-risk zone.

The novel entities index and the aerosol loading index display comparable dynamics, with a steady deterioration of the indices under GG, reaching values of 385 (for novel entities) and 264 (for aerosol loading) at the end of the simulation. Under DG, the index values increase until global output peaks, and then start to decrease, reaching initial levels for the aerosol loading index and a value 28% above the reference value for the novel entities index (Figure 3j and k).

Industrial green water consumption increases steadily in the GG scenario, despite an assumed reduction of green water intensity due to further industrialization of the global food sector, reflected in an increase of the green water index from 100 to over 200 at the end of the simulation. The blue water index that integrates industrial and household blue water consumption increases even faster than the green water index, crossing the lower threshold for blue water consumption around the middle of the century, and the upper threshold in 2076. In the DG scenario, green water consumption peaks in 2055 and returns to the reference value towards the end of the simulation while blue water consumption increases strongly until the middle of the century and levels off afterwards, entering the zone of uncertainty (Figure 3l).

Figure 3: Development of a) fossil resource use, including oil, gas and coal, given in primary energy and in EJ; b) non-energy fossil fuel consumption in EJ; c) the biosphere integrity index; d) the land system change index; e) the radiative forcing index; f) CO₂ concentration index; g) ocean acidification index; h) biogeochemical flows (N) index; i) biogeochemical flows (P) index; j) novel entities index; k) aerosol loading index; l) blue (circle) and green (cross) water indices. All indices are dimensionless and take a reference value of 100 in the initial year of the simulation. Red lines represent upper risk thresholds while green lines represent lower risk thresholds for various planetary boundary indices. Blue lines describe developments under degrowth, orange lines developments under green growth.

Figure 4 shows the initial values for every PBI compared to the operationalized upper and lower threshold values that are known (a), alongside the projected values in 2100 for both simulation scenarios (b), highlighting the substantial changes projected by the model. The results indicate that, overall, the GG scenario falls short of producing ‘genuine green growth’, defined as growth in output that delivers absolute reductions in environmental impacts (Stoknes & Rockström, 2018).

Figure 4: a) PBI values at the beginning of the simulation (grey); lower (green) and upper (red) thresholds for certain PBIs; b) PBI values at the end of the simulation for a Green growth (orange) and Degrowth (blue) scenario.

4. Discussion

4.1. Policy implications

Our results show that a DG scenario combining strong technological and behavioral changes with consumption reductions among richer households—to about €9,000 per person per year—outperforms a GG scenario not only in terms of resource equity but also environmental sustainability. Considering multiple Earth system variables represented through PBIs, we have demonstrated that GG strategies with a narrow focus on reducing the carbon intensity of the economy not only fail to achieve strong climate mitigation at the pace required to reach international climate targets but also neglect other important dimensions of global environmental change (Crona et al., 2023; Goodwin et al., 2024; Vitousek, 1994). Although our results should be interpreted as qualitative illustrations of global socio-ecological dynamics rather than exact quantitative forecasts, several implications for sustainability policy emerge.

First, significant mitigation of anthropogenic pressures on the Earth system requires a policy mix that combines green structural change with shifts in consumption patterns and social redistribution or changes in the property structure within and between societies. Given the limits to how fast and deeply the global economy can decarbonize and dematerialize, behavioral changes—such as a shift to plant-based diets and reduced private consumption by affluent households, especially in high-income countries—can slow the Earth system’s drift toward unsustainable states. For some planetary boundaries, these changes eventually might allow the Earth system to enter again into a lower or low-risk zone.

Second, economic development in low-income regions and rising living standards for poorer classes are shared objectives of both GG and DG paradigms. Growth and infrastructure policies should therefore avoid locking poorer regions into carbon-dependent infrastructure (Chen et al., 2021; Unruh & Carrillo-Hermosilla, 2006). Rapid and equitable growth in these regions requires redistribution within societies and capital transfers from richer to poorer territories at both regional and global scales. However, given the persistent scarcity of capital flows to least-developed countries (UN, 2024; UNCTAD, 2023), the DG scenario may face greater feasibility challenges. Another obstacle is the strong decline in government spending observed for high-income countries in the simulation, which, under the current international ‘rules of the game’ could undermine support for DG from the Global North’s governments. Thus, achieving better social and environmental outcomes through a global DG development paradigm may require a new global political–economic logic, grounded in a radically reformed institutional architecture.

Third, sustainability policies must address all Earth system boundaries rather than focusing solely on climate mitigation, which risks adverse trade-offs (Braun et al., 2025; Suckling et al., 2021). The deterioration of N and P related PBIs in the GG simulation indicates a continued reliance on industrial fertilizer which is not only problematic due to altered biogeochemical flows but also because phosphate resources are finite and industrial nitrogen synthesis depends heavily on natural gas (Mingolla & Rosa, 2025; Sverdrup & Ragnarsdottir, 2011; Vaccari & Strigul, 2011; Van Vuuren et al., 2010). Organic agricultural practices could reduce perturbations of the N, P, and C cycles (Scialabba & Müller-Lindenlauf, 2010; Smith et al., 2015) yet their widespread adoption remains constrained by current policy regimes, infrastructure gaps, vested interests, limited knowledge, and cultural barriers (Reganold & Wachter, 2016).

Finally, in neither scenario does the Earth system return to a safe operating zone, even under optimistic assumptions about productivity and bioenergy scalability. Most PBIs remain far beyond their upper thresholds—deep in the “high-risk” zone. This finding differs substantially

from GG simulations based on SSP2 and SSP1 conducted with the IAM IMAGE which show improvements for several boundaries, including climate change, freshwater use, and biogeochemical flows (Van Vuuren et al., 2025). Thus, we argue that it is important to assess the feasibility of global development within planetary boundaries by multiple IAMs that reflect a greater diversity regarding scenario assumptions and model structure.

In MORDRED, although the DG scenario performs better than the GG scenario, several indices - including blue water, novel entities, ocean acidification, CO₂ concentration, and radiative forcing - still deteriorate. Only two PBIs return to safe levels by 2100. This suggests that even ambitious sustainability strategies may be insufficient for full recovery. Consequently, policies must not only strengthen mitigation but also enhance societal resilience and adaptation to reduce the risks associated with prolonged planetary boundary transgression.

4.2. Limitations and further research

The introduction of PBIs represents a first step toward broadening integrated environmental assessment models to systematically include multiple critical Earth system boundaries. However, their development and integration into MORDRED were constrained by model structure and remaining knowledge gaps. For example, biogeochemical PBIs rely on global rather than regional flows, the ozone depletion index is assumed constant, and the 'novel entities' index is proxied by chemical sector output.

A key limitation is the absence of feedbacks from the planetary boundary module to the rest of the model. As a result, our simulations capture the effects of economic development on Earth system variables, but not the reverse—how prolonged boundary transgressions might impact economic and social systems. Future research should refine the representation of individual boundaries in IAMs and explore the socio-economic consequences of the Earth system remaining in a high-risk state for extended periods. Currently, the model distinguishes only between three risk zones—safe, increased risk, and high risk—making it difficult to assess how risk scales within the high-risk zone. Developing a more nuanced, quantitative understanding of these relationships is an important next step.

Further limitations stem from the assumption of a smooth, immediate global transition, high fossil resource availability, and rapid technological progress. Future studies could relax these assumptions by incorporating feedbacks that slow land productivity improvements and by modeling biophysical limits to organic agriculture and bioenergy scalability

5. Conclusion

This study compared the economic, social, and biophysical outcomes of two global development paradigms—degrowth (DG) and green growth (GG)—using an extended version of the MORDRED model that incorporates a Planetary Boundary Indices module. The DG scenario yields lower total output but higher equity, improving living standards in poorer regions and slowing (or reversing) planetary boundary transgression. However, these improvements remain insufficient to restore a safe operating space. In contrast, the GG scenario's continued consumption growth across all classes and regions leads to further deterioration of most PBIs, keeping the Earth system in a high-risk state. Future research should expand the biophysical scope of IAMs like MORDRED by integrating additional boundary variables and feedback mechanisms to better capture the nonlinear dynamics of long-term planetary change.

References

- Algunaibet, I. M., Pozo, C., Galán-Martín, Á., Huijbregts, M. A. J., Mac Dowell, N., & Guillén-Gosálbez, G. (2019). Powering sustainable development within planetary boundaries. *Energy & Environmental Science*, *12*(6), 1890–1900. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE03423K>
- Allen, C., Metternicht, G., Wiedmann, T., & Pedercini, M. (2021). Modelling national transformations to achieve the SDGs within planetary boundaries in small island developing states. *Global Sustainability*, *4*, e15. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2021.13>
- BGR. (2020). *BGR Energy Study 2019 – Data and Developments Concerning German and Global energy supplies*. Hannover. https://www.bgr.bund.de/EN/Themen/Energie/Downloads/energiestudie_2019_en.pdf;jsessionid=ADF18B2529B3E89FC705FDF390A57BA4.internet002?__blob=publicationFile&v=6
- Bilancini, E., & D’Alessandro, S. (2012). Long-run welfare under externalities in consumption, leisure, and production: A case for happy degrowth vs. Unhappy growth. *Ecological Economics*, *84*, 194–205.
- Braun, J., Werner, C., Gerten, D., Stenzel, F., Schaphoff, S., & Lucht, W. (2025). Multiple planetary boundaries preclude biomass crops for carbon capture and storage outside of agricultural areas. *Communications Earth & Environment*, *6*(1), 102.
- Chen, X., Li, Z., Gallagher, K. P., & Mauzerall, D. L. (2021). Financing carbon lock-in in developing countries: Bilateral financing for power generation technologies from China, Japan, and the United States. *Applied Energy*, *300*, 117318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117318>
- Cointe, B., & Pottier, A. (2023). Understanding why degrowth is absent from mitigation scenarios: Modelling choices and practices in the IAM community. *Revue de La Régulation*, *35*. <https://doi.org/10.4000/regulation.23034>
- Crona, B., Parlato, G., Lade, S., Fetzer, I., & Maus, V. (2023). Going beyond carbon: An “Earth system impact” score to better capture corporate and investment impacts on the earth system. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *429*, 139523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139523>
- D’Alessandro, S., Cieplinski, A., Distefano, T., & Dittmer, K. (2020). Feasible alternatives to green growth. *Nature Sustainability*, *3*(4), 329–335.
- Donges, J. F., Heitzig, J., Barfuss, W., Wiedermann, M., Kassel, J. A., Kittel, T., Kolb, J. J., Kolster, T., Müller-Hansen, F., Otto, I. M., Zimmerer, K. B., & Lucht, W. (2019). *Earth system modeling with endogenous and dynamic human societies: The copan: CORE open World-Earth modeling framework*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1909.13697>
- Drüke, M., Lucht, W., Von Bloh, W., Petri, S., Sakschewski, B., Tobian, A., Loriani, S., Schaphoff, S., Feulner, G., & Thonicke, K. (2024). The long-term impact of transgressing planetary boundaries on biophysical atmosphere–land interactions. *Earth System Dynamics*, *15*(2), 467–483. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-15-467-2024>
- Edwards, A., Brockway, P., Bickerstaff, K., & Nijse, F. J. (2025). Towards modelling post-growth climate futures: A review of current modelling practices and next steps. *Environmental Research Letters*.
- Engström, G., Gars, J., Krishnamurthy, C., Spiro, D., Calel, R., Lindahl, T., & Narayanan, B. (2020). Carbon pricing and planetary boundaries. *Nature Communications*, *11*(1), 4688. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18342-7>

- Goodwin, K., Li, M., & Wiedmann, T. (2024). Beyond greenhouse gases – Comprehensive planetary boundary footprints to measure environmental impact. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 52, 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.10.009>
- Gries, T., & Naudé, W. (2025). Economics for a Safe Operating Space: A Green-Growth-Degrowth Model. *Institute of Labor Economics (IZA)*, 1–55.
- Houtbeckers, E. (2025). Mapping the spectrum of degrowth work. In A. Nelson (Ed.), *Routledge Handbook of Degrowth* (pp. 292–306). Routledge.
- IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.
- Kallis, G., Hickel, J., O'Neill, D. W., Jackson, T., Victor, P. A., Raworth, K., Schor, J. B., Steinberger, J. K., & Ürge-Vorsatz, D. (2025). Post-growth: The science of wellbeing within planetary boundaries. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 9(1), e62–e78.
- Kikstra, J. S., Li, M., Brockway, P. E., Hickel, J., Keysser, L., Malik, A., Rogelj, J., Van Ruijven, B., & Lenzen, M. (2024). Downscaling down under: Towards degrowth in integrated assessment models. *Economic Systems Research*, 36(4), 576–606. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2023.2301443>
- Kronenberg, J., Andersson, E., Elmqvist, T., Łaszkiwicz, E., Xue, J., & Khmara, Y. (2024). Cities, planetary boundaries, and degrowth. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 8(4), e234–e241. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(24\)00025-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(24)00025-1)
- Lahoti, R., Jayadev, A., & Reddy, S. (2016). The global consumption and income project (GCIP): An overview. *Journal of Globalization and Development*, 7(1), 61–108.
- Lauer, A., Capellán-Pérez, I., & Wergles, N. (2025). A comparative review of de-and post-growth modeling studies. *Ecological Economics*, 227, 108383.
- Lauer, A., & Llases, L. (2025). *MORDRED: Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development. Model Documentation*. GitHub. <https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED>
- Lu, C., & Tian, H. (2017). Global nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizer use for agriculture production in the past half century: Shifted hot spots and nutrient imbalance. *Earth System Science Data*, 9(1), 181–192. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-9-181-2017>
- Mathias, J.-D., Anderies, J. M., & Janssen, M. A. (2017). On our rapidly shrinking capacity to comply with the planetary boundaries on climate change. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 42061. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep42061>
- Mingolla, S., & Rosa, L. (2025). Low-carbon ammonia production is essential for resilient and sustainable agriculture. *Nature Food*, 6(6), 610–621. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-025-01125-y>
- Moyer, J. D. (2023). Modeling transformational policy pathways on low growth and negative growth scenarios to assess impacts on socioeconomic development and carbon emissions. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 15996.
- Nieto, J., Carpintero, Ó., Lobejón, L. F., & Miguel, L. J. (2020). An ecological macroeconomics model: The energy transition in the EU. *Energy Policy*, 145, 111726.
- O'Neill, D. W., Fanning, A. L., Lamb, W. F., & Steinberger, J. K. (2018). A good life for all within planetary boundaries. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(2), 88–95.
- Reganold, J. P., & Wachter, J. M. (2016). Organic agriculture in the twenty-first century. *Nature Plants*, 2(2), 15221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nplants.2015.221>
- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., Drüke, M., Fetzer, I., Bala, G., & von Bloh, W. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458.

- Rockström, J., Gupta, J., Qin, D., Lade, S. J., Abrams, J. F., Andersen, L. S., Armstrong McKay, D. I., Bai, X., Bala, G., Bunn, S. E., Ciobanu, D., DeClerck, F., Ebi, K., Gifford, L., Gordon, C., Hasan, S., Kanie, N., Lenton, T. M., Loriani, S., ... Zhang, X. (2023). Safe and just Earth system boundaries. *Nature*, *619*(7968), 102–111. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06083-8>
- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F. S. I., Lambin, E., Lenton, T., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H. J., Nykvist, B., de Wit, C., Hughes, T., van der Leeuw, S., Rodhe, H., Sörlin, S., Snyder, P., Costanza, R., Svedin, U., ... Foley, J. (2009). Planetary Boundaries: Exploring the Safe Operating Space for Humanity. *Ecology and Society*, *14*(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-03180-140232>
- Scialabba, N. E.-H., & Müller-Lindenlauf, M. (2010). Organic agriculture and climate change. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, *25*(2), 158–169. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170510000116>
- Smith, L. G., Williams, A. G., & Pearce, Bruce D. (2015). The energy efficiency of organic agriculture: A review. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, *30*(3), 280–301. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170513000471>
- Stadler, K., Wood, R., Bulavskaya, T., Södersten, C., Simas, M., Schmidt, S., Usubiaga, A., Acosta-Fernández, J., Kuenen, J., Bruckner, M., Giljum, S., Lutter, S., Merciai, S., Schmidt, J. H., Theurl, M. C., Plutzar, C., Kastner, T., Eisenmenger, N., Erb, K., ... Tukker, A. (2018). EXIOBASE 3: Developing a Time Series of Detailed Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output Tables. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, *22*(3), 502–515. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12715>
- Steffen, W., Richardson, K., Rockström, J., Cornell, S. E., Fetzer, I., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., Carpenter, S. R., de Vries, W., & de Wit, C. A. (2015). Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*, *347*(6223).
- Stoknes, P. E., & Rockström, J. (2018). Redefining green growth within planetary boundaries. *Energy Research & Social Science*, *44*, 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.04.030>
- Suckling, J., Hoolohan, C., Soutar, I., & Druckman, A. (2021). Unintended consequences: Unknowable and unavoidable, or knowable and unforgivable? *Frontiers in Climate*, *3*, 737929.
- Sultana, F. (2023). Whose growth in whose planetary boundaries? Decolonising planetary justice in the Anthropocene. *Geo: Geography and Environment*, *10*(2), e00128. <https://doi.org/10.1002/geo2.128>
- Sverdrup, H. U., & Ragnarsdottir, K. V. (2011). Challenging the planetary boundaries II: Assessing the sustainable global population and phosphate supply, using a systems dynamics assessment model. *Applied Geochemistry*, *26*, S307–S310.
- UN. (2024). November 2024 Briefing: Economic prospects and development challenges in landlocked developing countries. *World Economic Situation and Prospects: Monthly Briefing*, *186*. <https://policy.desa.un.org/sites/default/files/publications/2024-11/mb186.pdf>
- UN DESA. (2019). *World Population Prospects 2019, Online Edition. Rev. 1. File POP/7-1: Total population (both sexes combined) by five-year age group, region, subregion and country, 1950-2100 (thousands)*.
- UNCTAD. (2023). Investment flows to least developed countries affected disproportionately by global crises. *Global Investment Trends Monitor*, *45*, 1–12.
- Unruh, G. C., & Carrillo-Hermosilla, J. (2006). Globalizing carbon lock-in. *Energy Policy*, *34*(10), 1185–1197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2004.10.013>

- Vaccari, D. A., & Strigul, N. (2011). Extrapolating phosphorus production to estimate resource reserves. *Chemosphere*, *84*(6), 792–797.
- Van Vuuren, D. P., Bouwman, A. F., & Beusen, A. H. (2010). Phosphorus demand for the 1970–2100 period: A scenario analysis of resource depletion. *Global Environmental Change*, *20*(3), 428–439.
- Van Vuuren, D. P., Doelman, J. C., Schmidt Tagomori, I., Beusen, A. H. W., Cornell, S. E., Röckstrom, J., Schipper, A. M., Stehfest, E., Ambrosio, G., Van Den Berg, M., Bouwman, L., Daioglou, V., Harmsen, M., Lucas, P., Van Der Wijst, K.-I., & Van Zeist, W.-J. (2025). Exploring pathways for world development within planetary boundaries. *Nature*, *641*(8064), 910–916. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-08928-w>
- Van Vuuren, D. P., Stehfest, E., Gernaat, D. E., Doelman, J. C., Van den Berg, M., Harmsen, M., de Boer, H. S., Bouwman, L. F., Daioglou, V., & Edelenbosch, O. Y. (2017). Energy, land-use and greenhouse gas emissions trajectories under a green growth paradigm. *Global Environmental Change*, *42*, 237–250.
- Vázquez, D., Galán-Martín, Á., Tulus, V., & Guillén-Gosálbez, G. (2023). Level of decoupling between economic growth and environmental pressure on Earth-system processes. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, *43*, 217–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.11.001>
- Vincent, O., & Brandellero, A. (2023). Transforming work: A critical literature review on degrowth, post-growth, postcapitalism and craft labor. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *430*, 139640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139640>
- Vitousek, P. M. (1994). Beyond Global Warming: Ecology and Global Change. *Ecology*, *75*(7), 1861–1876. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1941591>